

TECHNOLOGY OF PREDICTING WEIGHT-BODY INDICATORS IN THE SELECTION OF JUDOKA FOR LONG-TERM TRAINING

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Abstract: this article develops proposals and recommendations for improving the compatibility of methods of creating digital technologies for the development of higher sports achievements and the preparatory process by sorting and predicting in sports educational institutions.

Keywords: higher sports achievements, development, sports education, institution, selection, sorting, orientation, prediction, monitoring, introduction, control, complex, technology, methodology.

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ВЕСА ТЕЛА ПРИ ОТБОРЕ ДЗЮДОИСТОВ НА ДЛИТЕЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНИРОВКИ

Аннотация: В данной статье разработаны методики создания цифровых технологий развития высших спортивных достижений путем отбора и прогнозирования в спортивных учебных заведениях, а также предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию соответствия процесса подготовки.

Ключевые слова: высшие спортивные достижения, развитие, спортивное образование, учреждение, отбор, квалификация, ориентация, прогнозирование, мониторинг, внедрение, контроль, комплекс, технология, методика.

INTRODUCTION

The development of Science in our republic, conducting scientific research in every field and practical implementation of the obtained scientific results are considered as priorities of state policy. The creation of digital technologies for the development of higher sports achievements by sorting and predicting in sports educational institutions the preparation of talented athletes for competitive activities, the development of sorting into multi-year stages of training activities on the basis of novel scientific and practical approaches remains a requirement today. In developed mamalakats, pedagogical software tools designed to master educational subjects, in particular electronic textbooks and manuals, automated teaching technologies, electronic information resources have been created and are widely used in ham.

The use of digital technologies in physical education and sports their effective use is manifested in the scientific research of Soha scientists. But the fact that these electronic databases do not work in a holistic way, in addition, the development of a separate electronic system for sorting and predicting athletes for sports remains one of the modern sports treats. Sport ta'lim muassasalarida saralash va bashorat qilish orqali oliy sport yutuqlarini rivojlantirishning raqamli texnologiyalarini yaratish ustuvorligi:

- a new computer program for sorting action games specific to the elements of functional, physical fitness unicorn for sorting children into sports will be developed by adapting them to the technical elements of the competition;

- when qualifying children for the second stage in sports educational institutions, at the expense of determining the criteria and main indicators of physical fitness indicators depending on the weight category, a complex integrated assessment scale is developed;

- in sports educational institutions, when sorting into different stages of long-term training, a computer program is developed that predicts weight-height indicators;

- on the basis of monitoring the technical and tactical measures of the athletes of the national team, the development and effectiveness of a new model of sorting children into sports is based on experience;

Research objective. The Sport consists in the development of proposals and recommendations for the use of digital technologies in improving the compatibility of the stages, methods and preparation process of sorting, taking into account the indicators that affect the effectiveness of sorting and forecasting in educational institutions.

Methods of organizing research. The study used methods such as analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observations, questionnaire survey, pedagogical testing, pedagogical experiment, instrumental method, as well as mathematical-statistical analysis of research results.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our country, comprehensive measures are being implemented for the active development of the digital economy, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and areas, first of all, in public administration, Education, Health, Sports. Selection, sorting and Development Monitoring in sports educational institutions for the development of higher sports achievements will be established and organized compliance with the methods of qualifying stages, means, methods for children to sports, assessment of indicators of the preliminary preparation process and use of monitoring tests:

We consider this topic one of the most important treats today is very important not only in Uzbekistan, but also in world sport.

- compliance of methods of using computer technology to assess the indicators of the stages, means, methods of sorting children into sports in the selection, selection and Development monitoring in sports educational institutions for the development of higher sports achievements from the practical state of the art and monitoring control tests with the help of computer technology.

- tasks such as the development of a new model of child sorting and the justification of its effectiveness in experience, based on the monitoring of technical and tactical activities of athletes who are part of the national team, are being considered from the scientific unit.

- when sorting children into multi-year preparatory stages for educational activities, in exchange for the development of a program for complex integral improvement of qualifying stages, tools and methods, in the selection of children for sports, functional training, physical development, results of physical and special training, the selection system in connection with the results of competition activities, it is aimed to interpret the

Image-1. Qualifying criteria for sports wrestling

in the system for sorting children into sports, a new (champion) program for sorting action games specific to the elements of unicorn is developed, depending on the level of functional, physical fitness, at the expense of adapting them to the technical elements of the competition;

depending on the weight categories of the child, a complex integrated assessment scale is developed for the second stage of sorting at the expense of diagnosing five-level achievements and shortcomings in order to assess technical actions based on the criteria and regulatory indicators of general, special physical fitness;

Table-1. Analysis of weight-for-height results of the 2023 World Freestyle Wrestling Championships (Serbia, Belgrade) (n=347).

№	Weight weight (kg)	Total number of participants	Body length (X±σ)
1	57	33	160,5±4,3
2	61	27	163,6±5,7
3	65	45	169,3±6,3
4	70	30	173,2±7,6
5	74	45	175,1±6,3

6	79	27	177,6±8,4
7	86	48	180,8±6,9
8	92	24	185,5±9,5
9	97	35	186,3±7,4

When sorting into multi - year preparatory stages, the algorithm for determining the prospects for model sports is improved due to the development of model descriptions of control over growth dynamics based on weight-height indicators;

to perform the technical actions of athletes who are part of the national team, the number of total and successful attempts, the sum of accumulated points, the overall average assessment, the reliability of the attack, the possibility of qualifying at the expense of the development of mechanisms for the complex control of offensive level indicators will be improved.

The screenshot shows a web-based application with a table of athlete data. The table has columns for '№', 'FIO', and years 9 through 18. The data is as follows:

№	FIO	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
1	Абдуллаев Дитшод	125	129,971	134,477	139,881	146,216	158,636	162,344	162,344	164,422	165,58593
2	Рахманов Музаффар	128	133,091	137,705	143,238	149,725	162,443	166,24	166,24	168,368	169,55999
3	Холматов Азиз	130	135,17	139,836	145,476	152,064	164,981	168,837	168,837	170,999	172,20936
4	Рахманов Шокиржон	133	138,29	143,084	148,833	155,574	168,789	172,734	172,734	174,945	176,18343
5	Хамидов Музаффар	136	141,409	146,311	152,19	159,083	172,596	176,63	176,63	178,891	180,15749
6	Нуралев Муҳиддин	140	145,568	150,615	156,667	163,762	177,672	181,825	181,825	184,153	185,45624
7	Маллонов Дитербек	143	148,687	153,842	160,024	167,271	181,48	185,721	185,721	188,099	189,4303
8	Абдумуталов Шероид	146	161,807	157,069	163,381	170,78	185,287	189,617	189,617	192,045	193,40436

Callouts in the image:

- 1: Age categories to be included in qualifying for sports wrestling
- 2: Currently age of athletes when qualifying for sports wrestling
- 3: Currently height of athletes when qualifying for sports wrestling
- 4: The body length of athletes in the coming year, when qualifying for sports wrestling types (sm)
- 5: Computer program that predicts the body length of athletes in the future year in sports wrestling types, sorting

Image-2. Computer program that predicts the body length of athletes in the future year in sports wrestling types

CONCLUSION

Despite the systematic research carried out in educational and methodological sources, the topic of this study requires the development of additional scientific, scientific and methodological developments on the improvement of the system and content of child qualification in sports educational institutions for the development of higher sports achievements, the rapid development of selected sports, on the basis of new modern approaches in this field. Today it is known to all of us that new modern technologies and technologies are entering in the development of every field. The tools used in the sorting process, with their effectiveness, and consequentiality, bring a high degree of application in the field of sports. The use of these tools is of particular importance in the introduction of selection, sorting and Development Monitoring in sports educational institutions for the development of higher sports achievements.

Improving the compliance of the qualifying stages, methods and preparation process taking into account the indicators affecting the effectiveness of selection, selection and Development Monitoring in sports educational institutions for the development of higher sports achievements on the basis of innovative technologies and approaches by us, the development of electronic programs remains one of the top priorities in modern sports practice.

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